

A Mixed Reality eye-tracking investigation on key factors affecting food consumption habits*

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2

Abstract. This paper introduces a systematic method to study food consumption behaviors using eye-tracking within Mixed Reality (MR) settings. Participants wearing video see-through headsets are exposed to various food-related scenarios. Eye-tracking metrics, such as gaze direction, duration, and frequency, are gathered and analyzed alongside questionnaires about eating habits integrated with immersive data storytelling visuals relating to key factors affecting food consumption habits into the MR environment. The approach demonstrates how eye-tracking can reveal underlying preferences and biases not evident through conventional survey techniques, offering valuable insights for fields like health, nutrition, and advertising. Preliminary findings suggest a relationship between gaze patterns and food choices, influenced by dietary preferences, highlighting the utility of MR eye-tracking in behavioral research and dietary analysis. Specifically, it is shown that carnivorous participants display a significant focus on meat scenarios, while vegetarian participants are more engaged with more sustainable food choices. Furthermore, omnivorous participants showed a higher engagement with the presented key factors, possibly due to the complexity and variety in their diet choices. This differential attention underscores the potential for MR technologies to tailor educational and marketing strategies that are more aligned with individual dietary habits and preferences.

Keywords: Mixed Reality · Eye Tracking · Food Preferences Assessment.

1 Introduction and Related Work

Despite the ability of dietary habits to provide insights into the ways people choose, consume, and interact with food, researchers still rely on direct observations and self reported data collection, such as food diaries, questionnaires and interviews. Questionnaires are, extensively used for gathering large-scale data [1], but suffer from biases due to self-reporting and typically overlook the complex motivations behind food choices [2].

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Advancements in Extended Reality (XR) technologies, including Virtual, Augmented, and Mixed Reality (VR/AR/MR), have revolutionized the way food choices are studied by simulating realistic environments that allow for controlled experiments [3]. These technologies enable detailed analysis of visual attention, decision-making processes, and interactions with virtual food items through eye-tracking metrics such as gaze patterns, fixation duration, and pupil dilation. Such data provide insights into subconscious cognitive and emotional responses to food stimuli, facilitating a more objective study of dietary behaviors [4]. Furthermore, these immersive technologies have been used to promote healthy eating among youth, improve nutritional education, and investigate food cravings and meal selections in virtual settings [5]. Recent studies have shown initial findings in VR concerning behavioral factors in food choices [6], but comprehensive assessments of food habits using these technologies particular in MR settings are still limited [7]. In addition, there is a lack of studies cross-validating XR technologies with traditional methods, and a significant gap in using Mixed Reality (MR) for a broad and neutral evaluation of sustainable practices, presenting a distinct opportunity for further research.

This study addresses existing research gaps by integrating traditional questionnaire based data with eye-tracking metrics in Mixed Reality (MR) environments, aiming to deepen our understanding of demographic food preferences and provide a more dynamic, realistic evaluation of sustainable practices. This paper proposes a novel Mixed Reality (MR) assessment setup that effectively blends physical and virtual elements, thereby enhancing the realism of scenarios used to evaluate food habits and advancing our understanding of demographic food preferences. This integration enables the creation of environments that closely mimic real-life situations, providing a more authentic and engaging experience for participants. Furthermore, MR technology facilitates fast alternation among various scenarios and settings, allowing for swift transitions that are crucial in studies requiring diverse environmental contexts. This efficiency contrasts with the more time-consuming scenario changes often seen in Virtual Reality (VR) systems.

The adaptable methodology developed can be tailored to fit specific research needs and demographic considerations across different settings. By incorporating realism, rapid scenario alteration, and adaptability, this MR approach aims to refine the study of food preferences, yielding deeper and more actionable insights for promoting sustainable practices. By combining MR technologies and eye-tracking, this study analyzes key gaze metrics such as direction, duration, and frequency, to identify points of interest (POIs) related to specific food options. Key factors affecting food choices are derived from the questionnaires, and immersive data storytelling visuals are developed to highlight these factors in various food scenarios within the MR environment, helping to understand engagement levels across different dietary groups. 3D heatmap visualizations are developed to enhance understanding of dietary behaviors and identify factors that promote healthier, more sustainable eating choices, supporting efforts to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and advance climate change mitigation efforts.

2 Methodology

2.1 Background Description and Experimental Setup

Eye-tracking analysis focuses on critical metrics in MR such as gaze direction, duration, and fixation frequency to assess participants' engagement [8]. Research highlights these metrics' role in understanding visual interactions and decision-making [9]. This study adjusts gaze duration thresholds to differentiate between fleeting, brief gazes—lasting only 0.1 seconds—and meaningful engagements, thereby refining our evaluation of participant behaviors in MR settings.

XR hardware and the OpenXR software framework are utilized among other platforms, to perform detailed experiments in MR environments that track participants' gaze behaviors while interacting with virtual food items. The activities initiate with extensive questionnaires to gather information on participants' demographics, lifestyle, and dietary preferences. Participants from various food habit groups then engage in an immersive MR experience, where their interactions with 3D virtual food scenarios are tracked using eye-tracking technology integrated into the headsets. Data on gaze points are collected, including the duration, and fixation locations, and are visualized through heatmaps to highlight areas of visual interest. Additionally, quaternion rotation data is converted into Euler coordinates to improve the precision of gaze direction analysis that is essential for identifying focus areas within the MR environment.

An experimental flowchart that outlines these phases and methodologies is depicted in Fig 1, providing a visual guide to the study's strategy for examining the relationship between visual attention and dietary decision-making. The scenario is designed to assess the unbiased food preferences of participants by testing various food options in a MR environment. This involves creating the MR space and selecting appropriate food items to be displayed on a table, complemented by immersive 3D visuals for data storytelling. This setup is intended to facilitate eye-tracking studies within the MR environment, enhancing the assessment of how participants interact with different dietary choices and key factors affecting food habits.

2.2 Eye Tracking Data Collection and Analysis

Eye tracking data collection utilizes the Unity environment and the OVR Eye Gaze component from Oculus, integrated into a game object representing the user's eyes. Data analysis begins by processing eye rotation data where a custom script emits a ray from the focal point of an animated eye towards a target at a frequency of 50 Hz. Interaction points within the MR are logged when the gaze fixates on an object, like a food image, for a specific duration. The coordinates, time, and details of these interactions are recorded for further analysis.

Eye-tracking metrics such as gaze direction, duration, and fixation points are analyzed alongside questionnaire data to understand food choice behaviors. Three-dimensional heatmaps visualize this data to highlight areas attracting the most visual interest, providing insights into primary engagement points. By

Fig. 1: Extended Reality-Based Behavioral Analysis Flowchart: Identifying Dietary Choices through Eye-Tracking, HeatMaps and Data Analysis

overlaying these data points on food images, the study identifies food items and areas that attract significant attention, correlating these findings with self-reported preferences to explore underlying drivers of food selection behaviors. This integrated approach combines quantitative eye-tracking data with qualitative feedback to more accurately study food habits and preferences.

3 Results

3.1 Assessment of Participants

A thorough data gathering activity was carried out involving 115 participants. Initially, a detailed questionnaire was administered to collect information on demographics, lifestyle, dietary preferences, and health-related factors. The traditional questionnaire assessment revealed a diverse range of food preferences, underscoring the complexity of behavioral patterns in food choice and the importance of considering various dietary practices. Results indicate significant differences in gender distribution, BMI classifications, health concerns, and environmental considerations among carnivores, vegetarians, and vegans. Table 1 shows a higher proportion of males in the carnivorous group compared to the vegetarian and vegan groups, suggesting gender and cultural influences on dietary choices.

Several key factors influencing the food choices of participants were evaluated. Taste emerged as the primary factor, followed by health, cost, convenience, and freshness of ingredients Fig. 2. Additionally, the analysis revealed a higher prevalence of overweight individuals among carnivores compared to vegetarians and vegans. This observation is backed by various studies that link plant-based diets to lower body mass indices (BMIs) and improved health outcomes [10].

3.2 MR demonstration

Immersive MR content is developed within an MR environment to analyze correlations between participants' eye-gazes and these factors whereas tailored data-

Table 1: Comparison of Dietary Groups Across Various Categories

Category	Vegetarians (incl. Vegans)	Omnivorous	Carnivorous
Age Groups			
18-24	28.57%	6.19%	0%
25-34	14.29%	23.71%	14.29%
35-44	28.57%	56.70%	57.14%
45-54	0%	7.22%	0%
55-64	0%	3.09%	14.29%
65+	28.57%	3.09%	14.29%
Gender Distribution			
Male	28.57%	37.11%	71.43%
Female	71.43%	60.82%	28.57%
Non-binary	0%	2.06%	0%
Prefer not to say	0%	2.08%	0%
BMI (Body Mass Index)			
Underweight	0%	2.06%	0%
Normal Weight	57.14%	63.92%	28.57%
Overweight	42.86%	27.84%	71.43%
Obese	0%	6.18%	0%
Environmental Impact			
Very Low	0%	13.40%	14.29%
Low	0%	17.53%	28.57%
Moderate	42.86%	47.42%	42.86%
High	42.86%	19.59%	14.29%
Very High	14.29%	2.06%	0%
Health Concerns			
Very Low	0%	4.12%	0%
Low	0%	7.22%	42.86%
Moderate	57.14%	38.14%	42.86%
High	28.57%	42.27%	14.29%
Very High	14.29%	8.25%	0%
Ethical Concerns			
Yes	71.43%	27.08%	0%
No	28.57%	72.92%	100%

storytelling elements were delivered to enhance engagement Fig. 3a. The nutritional values of the main ingredients of the food scenarios were calculated using the NRF9.3 methodology [11], while estimates for CO2 emissions, water, and land use were derived from existing studies [12]. The user interactions (eye tracking, user clicks, gaze duration, fixation etc.) on the key factors affecting food habits are meticulously tracked within the MR setting. Table 2 shows the number of user clicks, the number of distinct gazes, the total, average and max gaze duration on several key metrics for all food scenarios for a carnivorous, a vegetarian and an omnivorous participant. It is observed that the omnivorous participant showed a higher engagement with the presented factors in terms of

Fig. 2: Key Factors affecting food habits of dietary groups

Table 2: Number of User clicks, Number of Gazes, Total, Average and Max Gaze duration on several key metrics for all food scenarios

Group	Factor	Clicks	Count	Total (s)	Avg (s)	Max (s)
Carnivorous	Health	20	30	9.70	0.32	0.68
	Water Use	19	69	26.24	0.38	1.58
	Price	19	65	28.58	0.44	1.16
	Land	12	60	20.78	0.34	1.28
	GHG	20	25	9.46	0.38	1.34
	Convenience	12	47	20.44	0.44	4.58
Vegetarian	Health	9	7	1.64	0.23	0.36
	Water Use	4	14	3.60	0.26	0.52
	Price	4	7	2.24	0.32	0.80
	Land	3	18	4.46	0.25	0.38
	GHG	5	17	3.88	0.23	0.36
	Convenience	5	25	8.28	0.33	1.00
Omnivorous	Health	11	69	41.08	0.595	2.88
	Water Use	10	66	35.60	0.54	3.64
	Price	13	69	38.72	0.56	3.46
	Land	10	59	33.86	0.57	2.80
	GHG	10	64	34.16	0.53	3.58
	Convenience	12	29	10.08	0.35	0.68

number of gazes, total and max duration, possibly due to the complexity and variety in their diet choices, indicating a potential significant concern about the sustainability of their dietary choices. In addition, the carnivorous participants' gaze in the MR was predominantly centered on the content displaying meat sce-

narios, more so than the vegetarian participants Table 3. This suggests that the MR environment effectively engages users whose dietary preferences correspond to the displayed scenarios. In order to better understand the visual attention

Table 3: Results of Number of Gazes, Total, Max, and Average Gaze Duration per Food Scenario at a sampling ratio of $f = 50$ Hz and minimum gaze fixation > 0.15 s

Group	Scenario	Count	Total Gaze (s)	Avg (s)	Max (s)
Vegetarian	Carbonara	2	0.42	0.21	0.26
	Lentil Soup	24	9.26	0.39	1.36
	Butter	10	3.72	0.37	0.88
	Beef Stake	13	8.06	0.62	1.44
	Bean Soup	5	1.62	0.32	0.52
	Buratta Salad	31	17.06	0.55	3.48
Omnivorous	Carbonara	39	26.54	0.68	4.22
	Lentil Soup	17	21.10	1.24	5.28
	Butter	14	8.76	0.63	2.14
	Beef Stake	21	12.68	0.60	1.78
	Bean Soup	17	8.76	0.52	2.24
	Buratta Salad	22	17.94	0.82	3.46
Carnivorous	Carbonara	29	14.16	0.48	1.80
	Lentil Soup	21	11.24	0.54	2.42
	Butter	24	7.60	0.32	1.02
	Beef Stake	41	19.28	0.47	1.76
	Bean Soup	25	12.24	0.49	1.20
	Buratta Salad	38	17.66	0.46	1.76

points, heatmaps were generated directly within the MR environment for an omnivorous participant, highlighting the specific areas where visual attention was most concentrated Fig. 3b. Furthermore, it can be seen that the carnivorous participant showed greater engagement with food consumption scenarios that are less healthy and less sustainable, which are particularly relevant to his dietary preferences. However, it is noteworthy that there was significant interest in the health, GHG and Water use metrics of his food choices, indicating a potential area to explore for educating such dietary groups about the environmental impacts of their choices.

One of the key challenges addressed was setting the MR scenarios to enable participants to interact with a multitude of food options within a diverse dietary content. To ensure the accuracy of this immersive experience, eye-tracking technology embedded within the MR setup was employed to measure participants' levels of visual engagement towards key factors affecting a variety of food items. The examination of eye-tracking data helped to clearly demonstrate individual profiles and visual biases towards particular categories and ingredients, allowing

(a) Mixed Reality Environment Setting with Data Storytelling Visuals

(b) Visual attention heatmaps generated within the MR environment for omnivorous participant.

further consideration of self-reported eating behavior as related to what people actually perceive in the MR world.

4 Conclusions and future studies

The assessment in the MR environment showed that individuals with sustainable dietary preferences spent more time looking at images of sustainable food options, demonstrating a stronger interest compared to those with less sustainable habits. Analysis of key factors affecting food choices showed that individuals with carnivorous preferences focused more on meat scenarios, while those with vegan habits showed greater interest towards more sustainable choices. To draw more definitive conclusions, additional research into qualitative metrics like selection patterns and physiological responses, including pupil dilation and heart rate, is necessary, highlighting the potential of mixed reality assessments to drive behavioral changes towards healthier and more sustainable food consumption. Future studies will expand these findings into immersive MR settings, using pupil dilation metrics to gain deeper understanding of the cognitive and emotional influences on visual attention patterns related to dietary decisions. Additional scenarios in MR settings will be developed, covering a range of consumer behaviors and habits such as circular economy and climate resilience, and data will be collected to assess how targeted campaigns can promote a shift toward more sustainable practices. Increased insights will be derived into how small-scale actions contribute to societal acceptance and a positive shift in sustainable habits

through better understanding of which actions and ultimately policies are more effective.

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